

Strategies To Overcome Leadership Barriers A Case Study Of Womenprincipals Inkhyber-Pakhtunkhwa

Maryam, Muhammad Idris, Abdul Ghaffar

Article Info	Abstract
<i>Article History</i>	<p><i>This narrative research focuses on different strategies used to overcome various barriers that are faced by female principals in Pashtun society. These barriers include societal barriers, cultural barriers, traditional role expectations, lack of mentorship, gender discrimination, sexual harassment, the glass ceiling effect and uncondusive working environment or tough working conditions. Different strategies that are used to overcome hurdles faced by women leaders contain changing the social environment. Changing the social environment means an aversion of the social environment by either changing the organization or migrating from the traditional social setup to urban setup. The second strategy is the familial support is also one of the main factors that help women remove their barriers in getting ahead in their leadership careers. The third strategy is an individual self-confidence. Improving self-confidence is a strong factor that makes a woman stronger in getting further ahead in her leadership career. The third strategy is the removal of gender gap. Gender gap has been erecting more and more problems for women in getting ahead in their leadership careers. Gender gap could be removed through academic credentials, professional experience and familial and organization support. The fourth strategy is self-determination and the fifth strategy is organizational environment. The more a woman is determined the more she is motivated to achieve higher position in her leadership career. Self-determination plays a significant role in developing a leadership career.</i></p>
<p>Received: May 05 , 2021</p>	
<p>Accepted: October 07 , 2021</p>	
Keywords :	
<p>Women Leaders, Female, Gender</p>	
DOI:	
<p>10.5281/zenodo.5555371</p>	

Introduction

Leadership is a vivid construction in human life. It is the act of proving truth and justice; developing a good relationship with subordinates to improve organizational performance; and the mutual process by which leaders provide good qualities to the followers of the organization (Gardiner, 2015). Therefore, leadership is not just about influence, but also cannot exist without influence (Surji, 2015). The leader plays an important role in the orientation and direction of the organization, which sets the vision and mission of the organization and others follow it. Therefore, an appropriate leadership style ensures influence and the prosperity and economic growth of the organization and staff. According to many researches, it has been verified that most failures in the organization come from the wrong direction followed by the leaders to achieve the goals (Meraku, 2017). Companies believe that leadership skills bring valuable assets to their companies, thus enhancing growth and revenue. So, companies around the world are spending billions of dollars on leadership training and development (Surji, 2015).

Women in Leadership

While women are largely underrepresented in leadership positions, the number of female leaders has grown rapidly in recent years, in response to active policies aimed at increasing female participation in key positions. The human resource management and psychology literature demonstrates that female leaders often adopt a uniquely transformative leadership style. Most importantly, transformational leaders greatly consider the needs of their followers and the development of good personal relationships with them. On the one hand, more and more people agree that women are better leaders than men. Contemporary women are well prepared for leadership, and there are some advantages that men do not have (Eagly, 2007). Women excel in soft skills and emotional intelligence, which may prove to be a major competitive advantage. A study found that women scored higher than men in all emotional intelligence skills, with the exception of emotional self-control; No gender differences were found here (Hong, 2015).

Women worldwide face great exclusions because of cultural beliefs that contribute to gender norms. Women in many societies face higher risks of poverty and social exclusion compared to the general population (Benschop, 2004). The problems they experience translate into homelessness, low education, unemployment, and then further exclusion from the property and inheritance decision-making process, which eventually leads to exclusion from most social matters.

The situation of Pashtun women is much worse than that of women in other parts of the world. Pashtun women are subjected to severe restrictions based on cultural traditions and the wrath of religious extremists. Pashtuns are very sensitive to the image and identity of women. There are pre-defined roles and responsibilities in the home such as child bearing, home preparation and food preparation which do not support his or her pre-existing rights (Jamal, 2016). Pashtuns want to educate women in the art of house making and discourage them to be like men (Boesen, 1980).

Thus, in Pashtun society the word woman is synonymous with "obedience" and "faith." She has to accept some of the harsh realities of a patriarchal society. The best Pashtun woman is a model of virtue, chastity and faith. She is expected to live up to the prevailing social norms, cultural values and ethics of the tribe (Ahmed and Akbar 1980).

The Pashtun community, which has endured the effects of terrorism in recent times and is still plagued by violent extremism, presents an excellent case to look at how the cultural factor hinders the contribution of women to the peace structure. According to a Pashto proverb, "a woman's place is a house or a grave." A woman's participation in a public issue is considered a disgrace to the family (Sanauddin et. al, 2015).

The glowing factual information highlights the status of women's rights provided by the Pashtun community system and life ethics by enforcing customary laws, which are mostly male dominated and Patriarchy in nature. The social structure of the Pashtun community is very congregation and women tended to live within the ideological realm of the Four Walls, which is said to be hers religious and moral place (Khan, 2016)

Problem Statement

The Pashtun society is highly sensitive on women relationship and socialization. This society is divided on different ethnic, racial and gender lines which make the progress of women hindered in every sphere of life. Since, Pashtun women are intersected by different racial, ethnic and gender lines, therefore, progress and advancement, especially of leadership skills is really hard for them. In addition, the Pashtun society is plagued by gender stereotypical perceptions that restrain women from getting further ahead in their leadership careers. Women leadership has been infringed upon by the prevailing gender stereotypical norms hindering them in their professional and academic struggles. The issue has been very complex and sensitive on the ground that every woman tries to keep herself bound to her family to fulfill the prevailing role expectations rather than developing her leadership career or getting further ahead in her leadership role.

In light of the above discussion, this study aim to highlight the barriers women face in the achievement of their leadership role in Pashtun society as well as identify the strategies through which such barriers can be abolished.

Literature review

Different strategies are adopted by women to tackle the barriers raised in the way of developing their careers as leaders. According to Abdullah *et al.*, (2018) cultural diversion is one of the main strategies adopted by women to remove the barriers in the development of their leadership careers. Cultural diversion concept does not mean changing the entire cultural setup which would probably take centuries to develop, however, many women in the global world try to migrate from one city to the other city to change the social relationship, identity and avoid the common perceptions of men against women in the social environment. This partial change in the role expectations allow greater space to women in developing their leadership skills or getting further ahead in their leadership careers. Zhong *et al.*, (2013) argued that women usually work for long hours in the organization which negatively affect their social engagements. While Jaumotte, (2003) argued that female want flexibility as a top priority in working condition in the form of health care benefit, flexibility in schedules, and create opportunities to advance their career in the organization. According to Eswaran (2019) organization needs to take some appropriate measures to create a supportive environment for female in a working place. In order to create a conducive environment for women would result in bringing more talented women forward to leadership positions. Jaumotte, (2003) argued that organizational policies should be more women promoting. It means that organizational behavior needs to be highly working friendly especially for women to bring them forward for developing and advancing their leadership careers. Eswaran (2019) argued that organization needs to provide equal opportunities to men and women alike without any discrimination with the aim to develop their leadership skills. Chen *et al.* (2020) argued that an organizational support to workers means boosting them up in their career prospects and development. Creating such an atmosphere for workers to share more experiences and knowledge with each other to increase their motivation and enthusiasm. According to Conti (2019) female leader who needs to equip herself with leadership capacity should join such an organization that promotes leadership skills. Eswaran (2019) is of the view that developing social and professional networking also help women promoting their leadership skills. Bowles (2019) argued that organizations needs to develop a proper measure to be helpful for a female to increase their professional ability and skill. According to Harvard Business Review (2019) organizations with gender inequality and discrimination need to enforce the law regarding gender-neutral.

The fact that advancement in leadership career is associated with the supportive role of husband is emphasized by Gordon and Whelan-Berry, (2005). The **supportive role of husband plays** a significant role in advancing leadership careers for women. Thornton, (2016) conducted a study on females avid to advance their careers in which he founded that majority of females revealed that the main reason of their career development was the

supportive role of their fathers. It means that familial support is highly needed for women in advancing their careers as leaders.

Axelrod, (2017) explain correlation between **self-confidence** and higher position in the organization. Improving self-confidence is significantly correlated to advancement in leadership careers. Grogen and Skesshaft, (2011) argued that women counseling at a workplace increases their self-esteem and confidence which has a very positive impact on their capabilities and motivation to get further ahead in their careers as good leaders. Heiskeneu, (2013) argued that many of the female leaders agreed upon with a mentoring factor which is highly effective in motivating and training women getting further ahead in their leadership careers. Mentorship plays a significant role in making women capable of getting further ahead in their leadership careers. Leadership advancement requires proper guidance and accurate directions that could be given only by an expert in the field. It means that expert opinion is really needed for women who want their leadership careers improved. **Self-determination** is one of the strong leadership skills that makes a woman stronger to advance her leadership career or skills. Talouselama magazine, (2013) survey revealed the findings of a study that was conducted on 128 females working on higher leadership positions that self-determination was the key to their success. They further revealed that self-determination is an imperative factor that makes women get further ahead in their leadership careers

Zhao, (2020) conducted a study in which factors like reporting against boss aggression, household responsibilities, fear of making mistakes, fear of making wrong decisions, unfriendly nature and more demanding were founded that negatively affect women leadership careers. Bowles (2019) argued that many barriers are found as unsupportive for female leadership career advancement. Some of the common stereotypical perceptions that negatively affect women are familial engagements, familial priorities, social role expectations, less supportive social environment and less organizational support.

Puriet *al.*, (2017) argued that many societies are **overburdened with stereotypical perceptions** which is one of the main obstacles in women leadership advancement. One main strategy for tackling this problem is to focus on men more than women in education and health. Because educated men give support to women on developing their leadership skills and careers..Kallio (2013) argued that one main factor that highly increases women capabilities in advancing their leadership careers is education. **Education is the key to a successful leadership career.**

The gender gap is witnessed in almost every society which negatively affect women and their struggle to get ahead in their leadership positions. Eswaren, (2019) argued gender gap or the development of male dominated perceptions or stereotypical perceptions in the societies constantly diminish career development prospects of women. According to the World Economic Forum, (2015) eradicating gender gap would probably take 70 to 107 years in Asia and particularly South Asia.

Methodology

The focus of this study was on narrative inquiry. Personal reflections of the respondents on their life experiences were the narrative in nature which is used for this research study. This storytelling technique was very adaptable to the social structure of the Pashtun people in the area. An efficient and effective strategy was to gain meaning from the respondents' explanations of their life experiences. As a result, emphasis was on oral history and narrative inquiry approach that was appropriate for this project. Ten female secondary school principals were selected for interview. The sample was chosen using a purposive sampling strategy. The participants were interviewed through open ended questions. The statements of the respondents were transcribed and analyzed. The statements were then categorized and themes were developed through codification and decodification .

Discussion

The previous sections thoroughly discussed hurdles faced by women in developing their leadership careers in Pashtun society. These hurdles included rigid working conditions, rigid cultural pattern, role expectations, the glass ceiling effect, sexual harassment, the red tape practices, the old boys network, gender discrimination and lack of proper mentorship. This section focuses on measures to overcome leadership barriers by women in Pashtun society. These measures include confidence building, strong communication skills, strong academic credentials, participation and exposure and collective consciousness. The last concept of collective consciousness is basically a socio-cultural concept. The rest of the four factors are endogenous factors. Endogenous in a sense that these measures are subjective measures which build women's skills for getting further ahead in their leadership skills despite of the prevailing barriers. Exogenous factors are related to the social environment. Collective consciousness means changing collective mentality of people in Pashtun society. Collective consciousness is developed through awareness and realization. Here human realization plays a significant role in developing collective consciousness. Consciousness develops such a pattern that is beneficial for the entire society irrespective of gender, sexuality and differentness. These factors are discussed in detail in the following passage.

Confidence Building

Confidence building plays a significant role in women's struggle to achieve a leadership position and promote leadership skills. The first element of confidence building process is sense-making. Sense-making is a process

of putting under consideration the common sense. Making a rational choice among the available choices. In Pashtun society, women can get further ahead very easily by building their confidence. Those women whose confidence level is high are comparatively better in dealing with situations of alert. They go very fast in ascending their leadership career opportunities. Confidence is very low among the Pashtun women and they face huge hurdles in understanding their career challenges. One of the respondents said that,

"I am a Pashtun woman and I work here in this school. I am happy to work on this position but one thing which I want to make clear that I am not confident".

Confidence is something that is rarely possessed by women in Pashtun society, however, those women who are confident are more successful in their careers. Confidence was lacking among majority of the women, interviewed in this study. It is because of the unfavourable familial background and schooling. Confidence, particularly general confidence, is developed through familial training and growth facilitation and proper schooling especially good kindergarten. Those women who belonged to good familial background were comparatively better in expressing themselves while those women whose familial background was comparatively not good and their schooling was also of mediocre standard, their confidence level was very low. They even could not express themselves the way other women expressed themselves. It means that self-confidence is such a capability that leads a woman to a higher leadership position. According to a respondent, *"My confidence is my power. I can talk to men and even express myself before other people whether they are men or women. I got this power when I was studying in the school. I know how to deal with people and how to compete. I am a woman but I do not lose my confidence whatever the situation or the problem could be"*.

Women who are confident are basically confident from their families. They are trained in such a way that they do not lose their confidence in situations of tension. In leadership, mental tension and pressure are both associated with managing things. When there comes extra pressure in the form of an internal conflict or huge economic cost, in such situations confident and steadfast leaders resolve the issue very easily. Low confidence in situations of extra pressure results in inaccurate decision-making. Inaccurate decision-making usually has bad consequences both for the company and the staff. A woman with strong leadership background has the ability to resolve the issue very easily. Two things are very clear from the statement of the respondent; one is strong background and the other one is high confidence level. Strong background means that confidence is usually learned in the familial affairs and once confidence is built, even hard tasks could be performed very easily. This reflects that confidence building requires huge time. It could be developed right from childhood. This is a skill that develops with the passage of time. This skill is highly required for women to tackle their leadership barriers. Barriers that are mostly related to leadership decision-making, conflict resolution, leadership advancement, communication and motivation could be easily removed by high level of confidence.

Strong Communication Skills

In this study, only 30% of the women had good command on English and Urdu languages. Pashto was their native language. They were all confident in speaking Pashto but only 30% of them were able to express themselves in English fluently. Those who were capable of talking in other than their native languages, were comparatively better in communication skills. Those who had better communication skills, their confidence level was higher than other respondents. Their strong communication skills made them reach to leadership positions. They were highly optimistic of getting further ahead in their leadership skills.

In Pashtun society, the medium of communication is Pashto or Urdu but English is also spoken. English is an official language and all official correspondence takes place in English. Women feel confident in speaking English and Urdu. Communication skills are necessary for improvement in leadership careers. Especially women are transformational leaders. Their leadership strategy is transformational and transformational leadership is based on strong communication skills in order to get the team more organized and motivated. Team motivation requires excellent communication skills to talk to the subordinates on high expectations and admiring their achievements in high with high standard of management.

Strong communication skills could be easily used to remove every barrier in leadership advancement. Women with strong communication skills know the tactics to resolve a conflict or compete with others particularly men in leadership improvement. Leaders with strong communication skills have direct link with the top executives because of their excellent performance in sharing updated information with them on high standard. One of the respondents replied to a question that why women are behind in reaching to top leadership positions?

"Women are left behind in leadership positions because of their silence. They do not possess excellent communication skills like men which is one of the main barriers in reaching to high level leadership positions".

It means that lack of communication skills is a barrier in getting further ahead in leadership positions. Women are though genetically soft communicators, however, lack of communication skills make them more vulnerable in managing their professional activities

In Pashtun society and even in other developing societies, where women are unable to express themselves quite clearly. These women are usually targeted for sexual encounters by men in their jobs. Here lack of communication skills makes women vulnerable for sexual harassment. It is also a barrier not to talk or express herself clearly. Here strong communications skills could be used by women to protect themselves in advancing

their leadership careers. It means that even a woman can protect herself from sexual harassment in the organization while possessing excellent communication skills.

Academic Credentials

Academic credentials give strong support to women competing on leadership positions. Men are comparatively more qualified and their higher qualification give them edge in the competition. Women are comparatively less qualified than men which leave them behind in the leadership advancement. Academic credentials play a significant role for women getting further ahead in their leadership careers. There are many barriers for women in improving or advancing their leadership skills in which low academic credentials is one of the main factors responsible for women neglected in top management positions. Academic credentials make the difference. One of the respondents said that,

“Women usually get that much education which could give them good jobs. Once a woman gets a job she does not keep her studies continue. This makes women left behind in the competition for leadership position. Every woman just completes her BA or MA to get qualified for a job”.

Every woman in Pashtun society, tries to complete only 14 or 16 years of education which is the basic requirement for a job. Women’s academic credentials, especially those who work in schools are not much higher. When they complete higher education they quit education and apply for jobs. In Pashtun society, getting a job means security for a woman. Every woman wants social security and status and both are associated with job. The following table shows details of respondents, their age and education.

Table 1: Details of women principals, their education, age & experience

Gender	Education in Years	Designation	Age	Practical Experience in Years
Female	16	Principal	44	12
Female	16	Principal	46	11
Female	16	Principal	42	13
Female	16	Principal	40	10
Female	16	Principal	52	15
Female	16	Principal	48	16
Female	16	Principal	45	12
Female	16	Principal	42	11
Female	16	Principal	50	13
Female	16	Principal	55	16

Participation and Exposure

In Pashtun society, women spend secluded life even in their organizations they try to be more isolated because of the prevailing stereotypical perceptions. This behavior makes them vulnerable especially in competition for leadership positions. From exposure an individual learns management techniques more practically. Those women who previously got exposed to situations of conflict, they were founded more confident in resolving a conflict in the organization. Exposure also comes through practical experiences. The number of years an individual previously worked on leadership position weighs more than an individual’s simple academic credentials without any past experiences. When academic credentials are not underpinned by practical experiences, it negatively affects individuals in getting further ahead in leadership career because leadership requires more exposure and participation.

Majority of the women had more than 10 years of practical experience but this experience was not on their leadership positions. Their experience was both on leadership and subordinate positions. Their practical experience revealed that their leadership skills had been developed up to a greater extent, however, perfection is hardly achieved by an individual in achieving a target. One of the respondents revealed that,

“My practical experience is my strength and I know how to manage things and how to get my team motivated for achieving the target. I have been exposed to different challenging situations which made me stronger”.

Collective Consciousness

Collective consciousness is basically the potential realization of the entire society. Collective consciousness requires collective realization that comes from the shared beliefs and ideas. The moral attitudes and standard of

the entire society changes positively. Through collective consciousness, every immoral belief and idea is set aside in the routine activities of life. Since, oversensitivity over women relationship and growth in Pashtun society is beyond human consideration and moral standard, therefore, collective realization would bring a positive change in the society. Every woman in the society is a social actor like a man and she needs equal attention, respect, opportunities, participation and relationship. Similarly, a woman should be provided every single opportunity of participation and expression in order to get further ahead in her professional career. Every barrier in the way of women leadership development could be easily removed through collective consciousness. One of the respondents explained that,

“I am a Pashtun woman. The culture of my family and my society is a bad culture. It is biased against women. Whether I am a good or bad woman but men usually look at me with their bad intentions when I come out of my house alone. I am not concerned with the men and their intentions but it erodes my self-esteem. At least I am a human and I shall be treated as human not other than human. How can I tell them not to look at me with their thirsty eyes. It needs collective efforts to realize that it is wrong to view women as strange”.

The Pashtun society is not entirely erratic but the common perception is developed in such a way that every woman when she goes out of her house alone or living somewhere alone is gazed by people as bizarre. This bizarre look over women in the society has been developed by individual acts which require collective efforts to rectify. It is not a social norm to keep women secluded or to look at them with bizarre eyes, however, these practices are developed by wrong lines. There are families who support women more than men to participate in their daily activities of life such as education, health and economic life. These families are though very few in number, however, they have developed a new culture of supporting women and giving them respect the way men are given respect in the society. This realization is though partial but it is converted into collective consciousness with the passage of time. The process of rectifying the social and cultural lines of the society is an exogenously induced factor affecting women in their choice of developing leadership careers. The society builds a specific pressure on women advancing their leadership skills, which could be rectified through changing the cultural pattern by bringing consciousness among people. Collective consciousness, as explained earlier, is necessary for removing the cultural barriers for women advancing their leadership skills. Women leadership barriers are almost socially structured which can only be resolved by improving human morality and shared beliefs and ideas.

Conclusion

There are measures which can be applied in order to get further ahead in the leadership career. These measures are both subjective and objective. Subjective measures are also called endogenous measures to tackle a problem or an issue while objective measures are related to the social environment. Some barriers in women leadership development are related to the social environment while others are related to women. Barriers that are related to the social environment are basically objective barriers such as harsh working environment, tough working hours schedule, huge competition, sexual harassment, role expectations etc. On the other hand, barriers that are related to women such as low confidence, promiscuousness, nonparticipation, less motivation etc are subjective barriers. These barriers require proper strategy to overcome. Subjective barriers could be overcome through strategies related to education, exposure, training and health while objective barriers require strategies related to the social environment.

The Pashtun society is historically ruled by tribal totalitarian leaders who developed their own agenda and supported that agenda through manipulation of the established pattern of the society. This manipulation of the established pattern of behavior diluted with the passage of time and it negatively affected the moral standard of the people. People adopted the manipulated ideas and beliefs which degraded their moral standard and this degradation later on resulted in the development new belief and ideas that were morally of low or no standard. This process affected their generations after generations which changed the collective behavior of people very negatively. In Pashtun society, when women participation and leadership is infringed upon by the common population it is because of the historical totalitarian background. Changing the historical pattern of the society would require rephrasing and refinement of the old ideas and beliefs to give rebirth to human morality, realization and consciousness. This rebirth of human morality and realization would result in women participation and development of leadership skills and careers.

References

- Abdullah, M.A., Hashim, H., Janten, H.A., & Islam, A.M, (2018). Factors Influencing Female Progression in Leadership Positions in the Ready-Made Garment (RMG) Industry in Bangladesh. *Journal of International Business and Management*. 1(1): Pp. 1-13
- Ahmed, Akbar S (1980). Pukhtun Economy and Society: Traditional Structure and Economic Development in a Tribal Society. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.
- Axelrod, R. H. (2017). Leadership and self-confidence. In *Leadership Today* (pp. 297-313). Springer, Cham.
- Benschop, M. (2004). Women's rights to land and property. *UN-Habitat Commission on Sustainable Development*.

- Boesen, I. W. (1980). Women, Honour and Love: Some Aspects of the Pashtun Woman's Life in Eastern Afghanistan'. *Folk*, 21, 22.
- Bowles, H. (2019). Why women don't negotiate their job offers. HBR Ascend. Retrieved from <https://hbrascend.org/topics/why-women-dont-negotiate-their-job-offers/>
- Chen, T., Hao, S., Ding, K., Feng, X., Li, G., & Liang, X. (2020). The impact of organizational support on employee performance. *Employee Relations: The International Journal*.
- Conti, K. (2019). Companies led by women have happier workers. What's the secret? Boston globe. Retrieved from <https://www.bostonglobe.com/business/specials/top-places-to-work>
- Eagly, A. H. (2007). More women at the top: The impact of gender roles and leadership style. WestdeutscherVerlag, Wiesbaden, Germany.
- Eswaran, V. (2019) The business case for diversity in the workplace is now overwhelming. World Economic Forum. Retrieved from <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2019/04/business-case-for-diversity-in-the-workplace/>
- Gardiner, R. A. (2015). Authentic leadership. In *Gender, Authenticity and Leadership* (pp. 10-38). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- Grant Thornton (2016). Women in Business: Turning Promise into Practice, 2.
- Gordon, J. R., & Whelan-Berry, K. S. (2005). Contributions to family and household activities by the husbands of midlife professional women. *Journal of Family Issues*, 26(7), 899-923.
- Grogan, M., & Shakeshaft, C. (2011). Women and educational leadership. San Francisco, CA: JosseyBass.
- Harvard Business Review (2019). Creating psychological safety in the workplace. Retrieved from <https://hbr.org/podcast/2019/01/creating-psychological-safety-in-the-workplace>.
- Heiskanen M. 2013. Hankalatämmät. Talouselähti, 26.4.2013 nro 17
- Hong, T. (2015). Relationship between emotional intelligence and the ability to influence.
- Jamal, A. (2016). Why he Won't send his daughter to school—Barriers to girls' education in Northwest Pakistan: A qualitative Delphi study of Pashtun men. *SAGE Open*, 6(3), 2158244016663798.
- Jaumotte, F. (2003). Female labour force participation: past trends and main determinants in OECD countries.
- Kallio, H. (2013). Statistics Finland. 2013. Two-thirds of mothers of children aged under three employed. Employment Statistics. Retrieved from www.tilastokeskus.fi/ti/tyokay/
- Khan, S. (2016). Impact of father education on female education in Pashtun society of district Charsadda, Pakistan. *Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 2(4), 1013-1019.
- Meraku, A. (2017). Role of Leadership in Organizational Effectiveness. *Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, Vol. 5, No. 11.
- Puri, S., Zhao, S. & Chandrasekar, A. (2017). The global Asian leader: From local star to global CXO. Center for Creative Leadership. Retrieved from <https://www.ccl.org/articles/research-reports/the-global-asian-leader-from-local-star-to-global-cxo/>
- Sanauddin, N., Khan, Z., & Ahmad, S. (2015). Women and armed conflict: Cultural obstacles to Pashtun women's participation in peacebuilding. *Pakistan Journal of Criminology*, 7(4), 141.
- Surji, K. (2015). Understanding leadership and factors that influence leaders' effectiveness. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(33), 154-167.
- Talouselämä, (2013). Naisjohtajien määräputoaaSuomessataas - "ensimmäinenkertaneljäänvuoteen" retrieved from www.talouselama.fi/uutiset/naisjohtajien+maara+putoaa+suomessa+taas.
- The World Economic Forum (2015). The Global Gender Gap Report 2015. Retrieved from <http://www.reports.weforum.org/global-gender-gap-report-2015/>
- Zhao, (2020). Overcoming Barriers to Women's Leadership & Unlocking the Power of Diversity, Center for creative leadership. IRC. global executive. Retrieved from <https://www.ccl.org/>.
- Zhong Y.G., Sue, C., & Blum, S.C, (2013). Factors Affecting Women's Career Advancement in the Hospitality Industry: Perceptions of Students, Educators, and Industry Recruiters. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Education*, 23(4).

Author Information

Maryam

Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Education, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan

Muhammad Idris

Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan

Abdul Ghaffar

Associate Professor, Department of Education, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan
